

Advancements and challenges in the development of a microwave imaging device to monitor liver tumor ablation

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Abstract— Microwave imaging (MWI) is a modality recently proposed as a way to provide real-time imaging of liver tumor ablation. In this contribution, the advancements and challenges in the development of such a medical device are reviewed and discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermal ablation is considered as an effective way to treat liver tumor, with a minimum invasive approach. At present, the real-time monitoring of ablation treatment is mainly relying on the clinicians' experience, because existing conventional modalities, such as computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), X-ray, and Ultrasounds (US), show several limitations in the clinical scenario. Microwave imaging (MWI), a novel technology that has emerged in recent years, shows promising features such as non-ionizing nature, portability, cost-effectiveness, and capability of real-time monitoring. MWI can detect changes of the dielectric properties occurring in the ablation zone, and hence provide information of the treatment stage.

So far, the majority of MWI systems were developed for breast cancer detection and brain imaging. Deep body monitoring (i.e., liver, kidney) was considered a hard task due to the high electromagnetic power loss inside the biological tissues. An initial feasibility study of MWI for liver ablation was given in [1]. The results evidenced that MWI can detect the transition between unaffected liver and ablated liver. The drawback of that study is that the antenna was not specifically designed for the system. Besides, improvements could be made to the measurement configuration. However, the positive outcomes of the study, pushed towards further

investigations, in particular looking for improvements to the system. In [2] some design guidelines of the MWI system for liver ablation monitoring were provided, identifying an optimal working frequency band (0.5-2 GHz) and coupling medium ($\epsilon_r=23$, $\sigma=0.07$ S/m). With respect to these working conditions, a compact antipodal Vivaldi antenna was designed. Such an antenna has an end-fire radiation pattern, which could allow several antenna elements to be placed in array configuration. Concerning antenna directivity inside the tissue, in [3] an antipodal Vivaldi antenna with cone shape dielectric lens was proposed, which could improve the E-field penetration inside the tissue as compared to the same antenna without the lens. In the light of assessing possible imaging algorithms for liver ablation monitoring, the study in [4] compared the performance of two inversion algorithms: truncated singular value decomposition (TSVD) and linear sampling method (LSM). The outcome of that study showed that the TSVD algorithm could provide more accurate imaging results as compared to the LSM, by using the same measurement configuration to image the evolution of the ablation zone. In the view of the above-mentioned studies, the in-silico validation of an experimental set-up was presented in [5]. To this end, an imaging experiment involving eight Vivaldi antennas in an array configuration and a practically realizable liver phantom mimicking the evolving treatment was simulated. Following the in-silico validation, the initial experiment validation of the MWI has been performed. The outcome of the experiment as well as the advancements and the challenges will be presented and discussed at the conference.

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